

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PHRASEOLOGICAL EXPRESSIONS IN THE MACEDONIAN AND THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE (WITHOUT VERB IN THEIR STRUCTURE)

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Abstract

This paper exploits the question of whether the English language has similarities regarding the Macedonian phraseological expressions and their grammatical and semantic structure. Since there is a vast range of phraseological expressions, the scope of this paper is within those expressions that are most commonly used in the newspaper sub-style. This choice has been made because of two reasons. Primarily, in the newspaper sub-style these emotionally colored language elements are constantly used for purpose of evoking certain reaction. Secondly, the Macedonian daily newspapers sometimes include phraseological expressions from the English language. This paper aims to provide a comparative analysis of certain Macedonian phraseological expressions (excerpted from several daily newspapers) with their correlates in the English language. The corpus comprises of Macedonian phraseological expressions that do not have a structure of a sentence, but are rather a combination of words that do not include a verb. In addition, their English language equivalents are provided. The paradigm of this research is qualitative, and the design is descriptive. The processing of data and the conclusion making process are done with the use of the following methods: analysis, comparison and synthesis. The research demonstrates that there are many similarities when it comes to phraseological expressions, even though the Macedonian and the English language belong to different subgroups of the Indo-European language family, and their cultures are quite different. The sameness or the similarities are not only evident in the lexical units but also in their grammatical structure, making the expressions completely or partially equivalents.

Keywords: phraseological expressions; Macedonian; English; comparison

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1. Introduction

People's willingness to express their thoughts in the most precise manner leads to the creation of phraseological expressions. The intriguing nature of these expressions introduces the outset of a new branch in linguistics named phraseology. This relatively new branch, which flourished in the twentieth century studies fixed expressions, i.e. phraseological units. It is said that a word group could be regarded as a phraseological unit if it is grammatically and semantically stable. This stability is achieved when the meaning of each word fades and a new meaning, which is partially or fully figurative, is formed. That is, the manner in which the words form inseparable connection within the group. In regard of the grammatical structure, the phraseological units in the Macedonian language may have a structure of a sentence, or they may be a combination of words that do not include a verb. For instance, the combinations may be formed of two nouns, two adjectives, an adjective and a noun, a number and a noun, or even two adverbs. Phraseological expressions are part of the cultural heritage that has been passed down from one generation to another. They provide a sense of identity and represent a valuable reflection of the history, culture, tradition and manner of living (Bojkovska, Minova-Gjurkova, Pandev, Cvetkovski, 1998, pp. 238-239; Velkovska, 2002, p. 7-14). Consequently, the question of whether other languages have similarities regarding their phraseological, grammatical and semantic structure is very intriguing. For instance, the English language differs from the Macedonian language in terms of the subgroup of the language family in which it belongs. The English language belongs to the Germanic subgroup and the Macedonian language belongs to the Slavic subgroup, which means they have many different features. In addition, they also differ in terms of history, culture, tradition and manner of living. Moreover, the English language is used all over the world because of the process of globalization. These are the reasons why this paper employs a comparative analysis of Macedonian phraseological expressions with their English equivalents. In this paper, the vast choice of expressions has been narrowed down to those that do not include a verb in their structure. In other word, the focus of interest in this paper is on the expressions that represent a combination of words formed with two nouns, two adjectives, an adjective and a noun, a number and a noun, or two adverbs.

In regard of the source, there are two reasons why the Macedonian phraseological expressions employed in this paper are excerpted from several Macedonian daily newspapers. The publicist style comprises the interpersonal communication in which one side has the purpose of spreading information about events that are considered important and interesting to a wide range of readers, listeners and viewers. This style includes the newspaper sub-style which aim is not just to inform but also to influence the public opinion, causing the reader to accept the expressed viewpoint. Consequently, despite the obligatory use of the standard form, the newspaper sub-style is also characterized by an extensive use of other language features. For instance, the need for an increase in the rating often leads to the use of emotive language, which elicits closer connection with the reader. Moreover, the author's willingness to evoke certain reaction and to reach the desired effect leads to the use of idioms and phraseological expressions. In fact, these emotionally colored language

elements are present in the newspaper sub-style largely. Thus, this is the first reason for choosing this source. The second reason is that the Macedonian newspapers sometimes include phraseological expressions from the English language. Namely, the authors do not only translate or transcript the expression, but they even go further and write the original expression written in English, mostly for stylistic purposes (Minova-Gjurkova, 2003, p. 284).

The comparative approach would enable us to notice the degree to which the analyzed Macedonian phraseological expressions are equivalent to the ones in the English language. In other words, we would be able to conclude whether they have complete equivalence, partial equivalence or they are not equivalent at all. The research shows two types of phraseological expressions. The first type is represented by expressions that have identical lexical units, which form identical grammatical structure. Those complete equivalents also have the same meaning. The second type comprises expressions that are partially equivalents, that is, they have the same meaning, but there is a difference in the lexical units or the grammatical structure. The third type of not having an equivalent (when the meaning is provided by an expression that has a completely different grammatical and semantic structure), which appears in the phraseological expressions that have a structure of a sentence (Janusheva & Jurukovska, 2017, pp. 410-425) are not found in the analyzed phraseological expressions. Comparison is a very productive approach because it allows us to provide valuable data. The obtained information would contribute to the process of gaining further understanding of the similarities and differences between the two languages. Additionally, it would also provide an insight into the problems concerning their translation.

2. Review of the literature

Phraseology has inspired many authors to explore its field of study. Many studies provide general observations and conclusions about the phraseological expressions in the Macedonian language. However, many Macedonian authors have also written research papers on specific segments of the phraseological expressions. In addition, they have included comparative analysis with other languages. For instance, there are papers in which the authors analyze expressions that contain certain components (such as words that refer to the human body) and compare them with other languages, i.e. with the Polish language (Gushevska & Labroska, 2016) and the Czech language (Delova-Siljanova, 2014; Delova-Siljanova, 2015). These papers stress out the similarities as well as differences between the examined languages. The Macedonian scientific literature also comprises of research papers about the grammatical and semantic structure of the phraseological expressions. There are even comparisons with the Italian language (Nikodinovska, 1999, in Bibliography 1987-2006), the Aromanian language (Hristovska, 2014), the Slovenian language (Veljanovska, 2000, in Bibliography 1987-2006), as well as the English language (Januševa & Jurukovska, 2017, p. 410-425). Furthermore, there are papers, which explore the use of phraseological expressions in different functional styles. Velkovska, (2015) and Savevska (2014) provide an analysis of phraseological expressions that can be found in the publicist style, i.e. the printed and electronic media.

Additionally, it is very important to emphasize that many foreign authors use the comparative approach and compare certain phraseological expressions from their language with the ones in the English language. For example, Fazlyeva (2015) makes a comparison between certain expressions in the Turkish language with their equivalents in the English language. Sakaeva & Nurrulina, (2013) compare Russian with English expressions, and Wolkosz, (2015) examines Polish expressions and their English equivalents.

This review indicates that the Macedonian authors have gained very significant insights into this field of study. We can notice that there are already papers with analysis of expressions excerpted from materials that belong to the publicist style. However, the expressions are not compared with their equivalents in the English language. Moreover, there are papers, which explore the grammatical structure of certain expressions, but they do not specifically refer to those stable word groups that do not include a verb in their structure. Finally, the research papers in which foreign authors explore the similarities and differences between the expressions from their language with the ones in the English language, and only emphasize the importance of this kind of comparative analysis. The English language is used all over the world because of the process of globalization. Consequently, we need to be aware of its important role on international level.

3. Methodology of the research

The paradigm of this research is qualitative and the design is descriptive. The corpus comprises of Macedonian phraseological expressions that do not have a structure of a sentence, but are rather a combination of words that do not include a verb, i.e. the word groups that are formed of two nouns, two adjectives, an adjective and a noun, a number and a noun, or two adverbs (Bojkovska et al., 1998, p. 224). In addition, their English language equivalents are provided. The Macedonian phraseological expressions are excerpted from several daily newspapers, published on the territory of the Republic of Macedonia. The processing of data and the conclusion making process are done with the use of the following methods: analysis, comparison and synthesis. The Macedonian and the English language belong to different subgroup of the Indo-European language family and their culture is quite different. However, the fact that the authors use phraseological expressions from the English language in the Macedonian daily newspapers indicates the need for further analysis. The comparative approach would enable us to note the similarities and differences between certain Macedonian phraseological expressions and their English equivalents in regard of their grammatical and semantic structure. We would also be able to conclude whether the analyzed expressions have equivalents in the English language, or they do not have an English counterpart. The proof that the analyzed expressions are phraseological expressions is their presence in the *Makedonsko-angliski rechnik na idiomi* [Macedonian-English dictionary of idioms – MEDi] (2002). Some of them could also be found in the *Frazeoloshkiot rečnik* [Phraseological Dictionary – PD] (2003, 2008 and 2009). The phraseological expressions are analyzed in the following order. First, we state the expression that is excerpted from the daily newspaper and we provide literal translation. Then we give the meaning that the

expression has in the Macedonian language with the help of the abovementioned dictionaries. After that, we provide the English equivalent with its meaning. For this purpose, we use the idiom section from the Cambridge Dictionary (CaD), the Free Dictionary (FrD), and from the Collins Dictionary (CoD). In addition, we make further research by using the Phrase Finder and the translation of the expression in the Makedonsko-angliski rechnik na idiomi [Macedonian-English dictionary of idioms – MEDi] (2002). Finally, we compare the expressions in order to determine whether the Macedonian expressions have completely equivalents or partially equivalents English counterparts or the expressions are not equivalents at all.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section of the paper, we provide the results along with the discussion. The analysis of the examples provides evidence of the many similarities between the Macedonian and the English expressions. Namely, the analyzed expressions not only have identical grammatical structure, but also the lexical units that are used to form the expressions are identical. In other words, the same word groups in the two languages have identical meaning, which indicates that they are complete equivalents. In addition, the analysis provides evidence of partial equivalents, i.e. examples, which have identical meaning in both languages, but are similar or different in terms of the lexical units that form the expressions. However, even though the units are not identical, it could be noted that they share many common features. This section contains of two categories: the first category is about the complete equivalents, and in the second one, the partial equivalents are provided.

4.1. Complete equivalents

As it has previously been stated, this category belongs to the phraseological expressions from the Macedonian and the English language that have identical units with identical meaning, i.e. they have the same grammatical and semantic structure. Again, we need to mention that the analysis is for those Macedonian phraseological expressions that do not have a structure of a sentence, but are rather a combination of words that do not include a verb. This means that the English equivalent also has the same grammatical structure. The information is given in the following order:

1. Citation of the excerpted phraseological expression from the daily newspaper (detailed information about the source of the expression are shown in parentheses, such as name of the newspaper, date of publishing, and page);
2. Literal translation of the expression in English (square brackets);
3. Explanation about the Macedonian expression in terms of its presence in the MEDi (2002) and the PD (2003, 2008 and 2009) and in terms of its meaning;
4. Its English equivalent is provided along with the meaning based on the MEDi (2002). There are also links of the English expression from the idiom section in the dictionaries (CaD, FrD, CoD);

5. Comparison of the phraseological expressions from the Macedonian and the English language, regarding their meaning, lexical units and grammatical structure is provided.

a) ... toa se prazni zakani ... (D, 2016, p. 16) [... they are empty treats ...];

Macedonian PE > *prazna zakana* (MEDi, 2002, p. 66) > meaning > *meaningless treat which is not going to be realized*;

English equivalent > *empty threat; hot air* (MEDi, 2002, p. 66); *empty threat* (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2esN9oD>) > meaning > *threat that is devoid of worth or meaning, one cannot or was never intended to be carried out*;

Comparison: *prazni zakani* = empty treats (Adj + N). The Macedonian expression and the English expression have the same meaning. Additionally, they have the same lexical and grammatical structure because they are composed of the same elements: the Macedonian adjective *prazni* is equivalent to the English adjective *empty*, and the Macedonian noun *zakani* is equivalent to the English noun *threats*.

b) ... na pregovarachkata masa ... (NM, 2016, p. 2) [... at the negotiating table ...];

Macedonian PE > *na pregovarachka masa* (MEDi, 2002, p. 115) > meaning > *a situation or place where people discuss with the purpose of reaching an agreement*;

English equivalent > *(to) the negotiating table* (MEDi, 2002, p. 115); *(at) the negotiating table* (CoD, <http://bit.ly/2fQBge8>) > meaning > *a situation or place in which people formally discuss something in order to reach an agreement*;

Comparison: *pregovarachkata masa* = the negotiating table (Adj + N). Same as the previous example, the Macedonian and the English expression have the same meaning, and the same lexical and grammatical structure, because they are composed of the same elements: the Macedonian adjective *pregovarachkata* is identical with the English adjective *the negotiating*, and the Macedonian noun *masa* is equivalent to the English noun *table*.

c) ... zad zatvoreni vrati ... (NM, 2016, p. 10 – retro news from 1994); UV, 2016: 2) [... behind closed doors ...];

Macedonian PE > *zad zatvoreni vrati* (MEDi, 2002, p. 24); *Zad zatvoreni vrati*. (FD, A – J, 2003, p. 121) > meaning > *without the presence of the public*;

English equivalent > *behind closed doors, behind the scene* (MEDi, 2002, p. 24); *behind closed doors* (CaD, <http://bit.ly/2ejn0VW>; FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fA9ovh>) > meaning > *hidden or kept secret from public view*;

Comparison: *zad zatvoreni vrati* = behind closed doors (Adj + N). As it can be noticed, the Macedonian expression and the English expression have the same meaning, as well as the same lexical and grammatical structure because they are composed of the same elements: the Macedonian adjective *zatvoreni* is equivalent to the English adjective *closed* and the Macedonian noun *vrati* is identical with the English noun *doors*. Here, the presence of the Macedonian preposition *zad* which is equivalent to the English preposition *behind* should be noted. In this case, we state that the grammatical structure contains of an adjective and a

noun but we do not mention the preposition as a primary element of the expression. Namely, the expression may contain prepositions or conjunctions but they are regarded as secondary elements whose purpose is only to help in the formation of the expression (to link the primary elements), or in its integration in the sentence.

4.2. Partial equivalents

This category belongs to the phraseological expressions from the Macedonian language and the English language, which do not have identical units or identical structure, i.e. the lexical units may be similar or different, or they may have different grammatical structure. The examples that are given in this section do not differ in terms of their grammatical structure, because they have identical grammatical structure. However, the lexical units in both of the expressions are not identical, which means that they are either similar or different. The information is given in the same order as in the previous section:

1. Citation of the excerpted phraseological expression from the daily newspaper (detailed information about the source of the expression are shown in parentheses, such as name of the newspaper, date of publishing, and page);
2. Literal translation of the expression in English (square brackets);
3. Explanation about the Macedonian expression in terms of its presence in the MEDi (2002) and the PD (2003, 2008 and 2009) and in terms of its meaning;
4. Its English equivalent is provided along with the meaning based on the MEDi (2002). There are also links of the English expression from the idiom section in the dictionaries (CaD, FrD, CoD);
5. Comparison of the phraseological expressions from the Macedonian and the English language regarding their meaning, lexical units and grammatical structure is provided.

a) ... na svoja raka ... (NM, 2016, p. 5) [... on their own hand ...];

Macedonian PE > pravi/prezema neshto na svoja raka/sopstvena odgovornost (MEDi, 2002, p. 180); raboti na svoja raka (MEDi, 2002, p. 181); *Na svoja raka* (FD, R – Š, 2009, p. 33) > meaning > *without consent or help from others, according to its own opinion, self-motivated;*

English equivalent > *do something on one's own responsibility* (MEDi, 2002, p. 180); *work on one's own initiative* (MEDi, 2002, p. 181); *on (one's) own initiative* (CaD, <http://bit.ly/2fhfmjb>; FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fA7HOB>) > meaning > *without requiring or having been given instruction, or guidance from others; by one's own effort or energy;*

Comparison: na svoja raka = on one's own initiative (Adj + N). The Macedonian expression and the English expression have the same meaning and grammatical structure (Adj + N), but they differ in terms of the lexical units. The first part of the expressions is identical because the Macedonian adjective *svoja* is equivalent to the English adjective *own*. On the other hand, the second part is different because the Macedonian noun *raka* (*hand*) is different from the English noun *initiative* because they signify different things or ideas. In this example, there is a presence of the Macedonian preposition *na* which is equivalent to the English preposition *on*. However, it is not considered as an essential component of the structure, but a secondary element that helps in the integration of the expression in the sentence.

b) ... od mali noze ... (D, 2014, p. 12; NM, 2013, p. 8) [... from small legs ...];
Macedonian PE > *od mali noze* (MEDi, 2002, p. 137); *Od mali (najmali) noze.* (FD, K – P, 2008, p. 246) > meaning > *from a little child, from a very young age*;
English equivalent > *from a tender age* (MEDi, 2002, p. 137); *tender age* (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fv9JdJ>) > meaning > *a young age*;
Comparison: *od mali noze* = *tender age* (Adj + N). The Macedonian expression and the English expression have the same meaning and grammatical structure (Adj + N), but they differ in terms of the lexical units. The first part of the expressions is similar because the Macedonian adjective *mali* is identical with the English adjectives *small*, *little*, and, in this context, we may say that the adjective *tender* (with its meaning *young*) could be regarded as a synonym. On the other hand, the second part is different because the Macedonian noun *noze* (*legs, feet*) and the English noun *age* signify different things or ideas.

c) ... da dochekaat dlaboka starost... (D, 2014, p. 17) [... to experience old age ...];
Macedonian PE > *dozhivuva dlaboka/dolga starost* (MEDi, 2002, p. 210) > meaning > *very old*;
English equivalent > *live to a ripe old age* (MEDi, 2002, p. 210); *a ripe old age* (CaD, <http://bit.ly/2e6CCAQ>; FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fhiZDk>) > meaning > *the condition of being very old; a long lifespan*;
Comparison: *dlaboka starost* = *a ripe old age* (Adj + N). In his dictionary, the author Murgoski, includes a verb as part of the expression, and provides translation, which contains a verb: *dozhivuva dlaboka/dolga starost* – *to live to a ripe old age*, (MEDi, 2002, p. 210). However, the example from the newspaper demonstrates that the verb can vary because *dochekaat* (D, 2014, p. 17) and *dozhivuva* (MEDi, 2002, p. 210) are different verbs that are used with the same expression. In fact, on this occasion they could be regarded as synonyms. This means that the Macedonian expression is formed of an adjective (*dlaboka*) and a noun (*starost*), whereas the verb can differ depending on the context. In addition, if the verb is considered as an element of the phraseological expression, then this phraseological expression would not belong to this group, but rather to the phraseological expressions that have a structure of a sentence. Therefore, it is very important to discover the real structure of the phraseological expressions. In regard of the English expression, in the two dictionaries, the expression is not written with a verb (*a ripe old age*). The examples in them have different verbs: *I'm sure he'll live to a ripe old age*; *My grandmother died at the ripe old age of 92* (CaD, <http://bit.ly/2e6CCAQ>); *All the Smiths seem to reach a ripe old age* (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fhiZDk>). This indicates that the English expression, same as the Macedonian expression, does not have a structure of a sentence, but rather it consists of an adjective (*ripe*) and a noun (*old age*). In terms of the lexical structure, there are similarities because the second part is identical, that is, the Macedonian noun *starost* is identical with the English noun *old age*. The first part is slightly different because the Macedonian adjective *dlaboka* translates as *deep*, and not as *ripe*. However, both adjectives have figurative sense, since we are talking about phraseological expressions. For instance, the English adjective *ripe* has figurative connotation because it is assigned to something that is “fully developed physically and mentally” (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fhiZDk>). The same happens with the Macedonian adjective *deep* which is used

with the figurative sense “of great intensity”, rather than its literal meaning referring to “a particular distance from the top to the bottom of something”.

d) ... Srekja vo nesrekja e shto ... (D, 2016, p. 18) [... fortune in misfortune is that ...];

Macedonian PE > *srekja vo nesrekja* (MEDi, 2002, p. 208) > meaning > *even though something bad happened, still something good came out of it;*

English equivalent > *a blessing in disguise* (MEDi, 2002: 208); *blessing in disguise* (CaD, <http://bit.ly/2fj7HuY>; FrD, <http://bit.ly/2esNMP1>) > meaning > *something that seems bad at first, but causes something good to happen; turns out to be beneficial; a misfortune that unexpectedly turns into good fortune;*

Comparison: *srekja vo nesrekja* = blessing in disguise (N + N). The Macedonian expression and the English expression have the same meaning and grammatical structure (N + N), but they differ in terms of their lexical units. The first part of the expressions is similar because the Macedonian noun *srekja* (fortune) is synonymous with the English noun *blessing*. The noun *srekja* can also be translated as *luck* or *blessing*, thus both nouns (the Macedonian and the English) refer to the same idea. On the other hand, the second part is different because the Macedonian noun *nesrekja* (misfortune) and the English noun *disguise* refer to different things or ideas.

e) ..., togash kupuvate „machka vo vrekja“... (D, 2014, p. 8) [..., then you are buying “a cat in a sack” ...];

Macedonian PE > *kupuva machka vo vrekja* (MEDi, 2002, p. 116); *Machka vo vrekja* (FD, K – P, 2008: 163) > meaning > *something unseen, unfamiliar, with unchecked quality;*

English equivalent > *buy a pig in a poke* (MEDi, 2002, p. 116); *a pig in a poke* (CaD, <http://bit.ly/2f6kow8>; FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fk0AXb>) > meaning > *something that you buy or accept without first seeing it or finding out if it is good;*

Comparison: *machka vo vrekja* = a pig in a poke (N + N). In the example, we can notice that the expression is in double quotation marks. We must indicate that double or single quotation marks should not be used with this kind of expressions, thus we must address the necessity of being more careful when using them (Orthography, 2015: 123–126). Furthermore, we can notice that the verb *kupuvate* (you are buying) is not included in the double quotation marks, but the authors put only the words *machka vo vrekja*. This means that the expression does not contain a verb, but rather two nouns (*machka, vrekja*) connected with the preposition *vo* (in). On the other hand, the author Murgoski, includes the verb in the expression, and provides translation with the verb included: *kupuva machka vo vrekja* – to buy a pig in a poke, (MEDi, 2002, p. 116). However, the English equivalent does not include the verb because, as it can be seen from the meaning, you can either *buy* it or *accept* it. The different verbs that are used in the examples in one of the dictionaries: *When you buy a used car, you might be getting a pig in a poke; Clothes from catalogue are a pig in a poke* (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fk0AXb>) lead to the conclusion that the verb *buy* is not an obligatory part of the expression. Consequently, we can state that the Macedonian expression and its English equivalent have the same grammatical structure (N + N). Regarding the lexical structure, the first part is different because the

Macedonian noun *machka* signifies a *cat* and not a *pig*. Nonetheless, the two nouns refer to a kind of animal. Moreover, the second part is similar because the Macedonian noun *vrekja* (*sack, bag*) has the same meaning as the English noun *poke* (word with French origin), i.e. they have a synonymous relation.

f) ... vo trka so vremeto ... (NM, 2016, p. 15) [... in a race with the time ...];

Macedonian PE > (*vo*) *trka so vreme* (MEDi, 2002, p. 223) > meaning > *the act of trying to do something very quickly or to be always informed*;

English equivalent > *race against time, race against the clock* (MEDi, 2002, p. 223); *against the clock* (CaD, <http://bit.ly/2edhyc4>); (*a*) *race against the clock* (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2fuYGkS>); (*a*) *race against time* (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2ft3Y1T>) > meaning > (noun) *an attempt to accomplish something in a short amount of time*; (verb) *to act quickly to accomplish something in a short amount of time*;

Comparison: *vo trka so vremeto* = a race against time (N + N). This example is very interesting for observation in terms of the grammatical structure. In this particular case, the Macedonian expression is composed of two nouns: *trka* and *vreme* (*race* and *time*) connected with the preposition *so* (*with*). The first word *trka* (*race*) is preceded by the preposition *vo* (*in*) which confirms that *trka* in this case is a noun (*a race*), and not a verb (*to race*). However, there is also the possibility for the word *trka* to be used as a verb (*to race*). The same situation is evident in the English expression because the dictionaries provide the two possibilities. Regarding the lexical structure, the first part is identical because the Macedonian noun *trka* is translated as *race*. On the other hand, the second part is slightly different because the Macedonian noun *vreme* (*time*) does not have the same meaning as the English noun *clock*. However, the word *clock* is closely related to the idea of time. Also, in one of the English dictionaries, there is the variation (*a*) *race against time* (FrD, <http://bit.ly/2ft3Y1T>), so we can confirm that the Macedonian expression and English expressions have similar lexical structure.

5. Conclusion

The intriguing nature of the phraseological expressions is once again confirmed with this analysis. The comparative approach enables us to conclude that there are many similarities between the Macedonian and the English language in regard of the phraseological expressions (word group), even though the two languages belong to different subgroup of the Indo-European language family. In addition, the culture in which they have developed, and the manner of living of the people who use them are quite different. The sameness or the similarities of the expressions are not only evident in the lexical units but also in their grammatical structure, making the expressions completely or partially equivalents. The first category of expressions, i.e. the complete equivalents, confirms the existence of phraseological expressions that are identical, even though they are from different languages. In other words, they are formed with identical units that form the same grammatical structure and provide identical meaning in both languages. When talking about partial equivalents it should be emphasized that, the partial equivalence of the analyzed expressions

is only consisted in the lexical units and not in the grammatical structure. Consequently, all of the analyzed expressions are a combination of words that do not include a verb in both languages. Non-equivalents are not found in this research, regarding these phraseological expressions. The most common expressions represent a combination of either an adjective and a noun, or two nouns. The results show that some phraseological expressions seem to have a structure of a sentence, but their further analysis indicates that they have a structure of a word group. This should be address with great attention. In regard of the similarities, differences, and we may also say the variations in the lexical units, it should be taken into consideration that the phraseological expressions are reflection of the culture and the manner of living. Thus, the existence of some lexical unit in the expression instead of another provides a valuable insight into the uniqueness of the people who use them. This is evident even in the same culture and the same language. These expressions are passed down from one generation to another, but that does not mean they have stayed the same from the moment when they were formed until the present time. They have surely survived modifications so that they would be more compatible for the time in which they are used. As confirmed by Velkovska (2015), some of the objects that the lexical units represent may be changed, or they may not even exist anymore, which means that the phraseological expressions always adapt to the changes in society. Furthermore, some of the lexical units are similar and, as such, considered synonyms. In addition, for the different lexical units, it can be noted that some of them are not that different, because their figurative meanings are closely related and present similar ideas.

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